

Syntheses, molecular and crystalline architectures of dinuclear mercury(II) halides containing a tetradentate tripodal amine

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Abstract : Two dinuclear mercury(II) halide complexes of the type $[(L)Hg(\mu-X)HgX_3]$ ($L =$ tris(2-aminoethyl)amine, **1**; $X = Cl^-$, **2**; $X = Br^-$) have been synthesized and X-ray crystallographically characterized. Structural analyses show that **1** and **2** contain two different halide bridged mercury(II) centers, with HgN_4X distorted trigonal bipyramidal and HgX_4 tetrahedral chromophores, respectively. Weak intermolecular $N-H\cdots Cl/Br$ and $C-H\cdots Cl/Br$ hydrogen bonds in **1** and **2** promote dimensionalities. The compounds show reasonable thermal stability.

Keywords : Mercury(II) halide, dinuclear compound, tripodal amine, X-ray structure, thermal behavior.

Introduction

Design and synthesis^{1,2} of mono-, di- and polynuclear coordination compounds of mercury(II)³⁻⁶ is the center of attraction for the preparation of different functional materials⁷⁻¹⁰ coupled with interesting electronic and optoelectronic properties^{10,11-13}. The sheer necessity for such research is the judicious choice¹⁴ of organic spacers and bridging units that may lead to directed properties. One-pot synthesis¹⁵ of the molecular components is an efficient synthetic approach towards preparation of such materials. Utilizing the veracities of coordination geometries around this $5d^{10}$ ion, diverse molecular and crystalline architectures^{16,17} of different shapes and sizes¹⁸ may be accessed through strong metal-ligand covalent bonds¹⁹ and multiple weak non-covalent forces²⁰⁻²². Polyamines²³⁻²⁵ with bifunctional behaviors may fulfill the coordination sites around the metal ion and assist in non-covalent forces such as hydrogen bonds²⁰ to form a plethora of supramolecular entities with different superstructures. Halides²⁶⁻²⁸ are suitable terminal/bridging units which in combination with organic ligands result in different molecular architectures through its versatile ligational modes. Recently, we have reported the syntheses and structural characterizations of cadmium(II) and mercury(II) iodide compounds^{29,30} in combination with tris(2-aminoethyl)amine. In our present endeavor, we have

chosen the same polyamine, (L , Scheme 1) to isolate mercury(II) halide compounds. Successfully, we have prepared two neutral mercury(II) halide compounds of the type $[(L)Hg(\mu-X)HgX_3]$ (**1**; $X = Cl^-$, **2**; $X = Br^-$). The syntheses, molecular and crystalline architectures, and thermal behaviors of these compounds are described below.

Scheme 1

Results and discussion

Synthesis and formulation :

The halide bridged dinuclear compounds **1** and **2** have been prepared using 2 : 1 molar ratio of $HgCl_2/HgBr_2$ and L in methanolic solutions at room temperature. All the reactions are reproducible as is evident from repetitive microanalytical results, spectral behaviours and other physicochemical properties. The details of the reactions are summarized in eq. (1) :

The new complexes were characterized by microanalytical (C, H and N), spectroscopic, thermal and other physicochemical results. The microanalytical data are in good conformity with the formulations **1** and **2**. The moisture-insensitive complexes are stable over long periods of time in powdery and crystalline states and are soluble in water and in organic solvents like methanol, ethanol, acetonitrile, dimethylformamide and dimethylsulphoxide. In MeCN solutions they behave non-electrolytes, as reflected from their low conductivity values ($\sim 5 \Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$)³¹.

Spectroscopic studies :

The $\nu(\text{N-H})$ stretching frequencies of the tripodal amine are seen in the range $3150\text{--}3340 \text{ cm}^{-1}$. Weak bands in the range $2920\text{--}2980 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ are assignable to the aliphatic C-H stretching frequencies. All other characteristic organic ligand vibrations³² are seen in the range $600\text{--}1600 \text{ cm}^{-1}$. In DMF solutions, the complexes **1** and **2** show maximum absorptions $\sim 260 \text{ nm}$ assignable to ligand based $n\text{-}\pi^*/\pi\text{-}\pi^*$ transition³³.

Thermal behaviors :

To examine thermal stabilities of compounds **1** and **2**, thermogravimetric analyses (TG) were made between $30\text{--}700 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ in the static atmosphere of nitrogen at a heating rate of $10 \text{ }^\circ\text{C min}^{-1}$. The TG curve (Fig. 1) indicate that the complex **1** is stable up to $174 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ and decomposes

completely between $174\text{--}594 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ with no residual part remaining after total decomposition (calcd. : $\text{L} + 4 \text{ Cl} + 2 \text{ HgO} = 104.63\%$; obs. : 99.48%). This may be due to the evaporation of the final residue (probably HgO) at higher temperature. Compound **2** is stable up to $186 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$; the TG curve (Fig. 2) indicates that its decomposition takes place in one step between $186\text{--}599 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ corresponding to the loss of one polyamine (L) and four bromide groups, and here also no residual part left after total decomposition (calcd. : $\text{L} + 4 \text{ Br} + 2 \text{ HgO} = 103.64\%$; obs. : 98.34%).

Crystal structures :

In order to define the coordination spheres conclusively, single-crystal X-ray diffraction studies of **1** and **2** were made. Displacement ellipsoid diagrams with atom labeling schemes and perspective views of the crystal structures of **1** and **2** are shown in Figs. 3–6. Selected bond distances, angles are given in Tables 1 and 2 and hydrogen bonds in Table 3.

$[(\text{L})\text{Hg}(\mu\text{-Cl})\text{HgCl}_3]$ (**1**) and $[(\text{L})\text{Hg}(\mu\text{-Br})\text{HgBr}_3]$ (**2**) :

The asymmetric unit of **1** consists of neutral $[(\text{L})\text{Hg}(\mu\text{-Cl})\text{HgCl}_3]$ molecule (Fig. 3), whereas compound **2** contains two neutral $[(\text{L})\text{Hg}(\mu\text{-Br})\text{HgBr}_3]$ molecules (Fig. 4) in the unit cell. Each dinuclear unit has two mercury(II) centers (Hg1 and Hg2 in **1**; Hg3 and Hg4 in unit 1 and Hg5 and Hg6 in unit 2 of **2**) with different geometries.

Fig. 1. Thermal behavior of **1**.

Fig. 2. Thermal behavior of **2**.

Fig. 3. ORTEP representation of **1** with 30% thermal ellipsoid probability.

mophores, respectively. Hg2 in **1** and Hg4 in unit 1, Hg6 in unit 2 of **2** adopt distorted tetrahedral geometry with HgCl_4 and HgBr_4 chromophores, respectively. Within each dinuclear unit, the two different mercury(II) centers are connected through a halide ion with bridging angles Hg1/Cl4/Hg2 of $102.28(8)^\circ$ in **1**, Hg3/Br1/Hg4 of $98.06(8)^\circ$ in unit 1 and Hg5/Br5/Hg6 of $98.42(7)^\circ$ in unit 2 of **2**. The ethylenic arms of L in each unit are to some extent puckered. In the dinuclear units, Hg1...Hg2 in **1**, Hg3...Hg4 in unit 1 and Hg5...Hg6 in unit 2 of **2**

Fig. 4. ORTEP diagram of **2** (10% thermally ellipsoid).

Hg1 in **1** ($\tau = 0.89$)³⁴ and Hg3 in unit 1 ($\tau = 0.94$), Hg5 in unit 2 ($\tau = 0.86$) of **2** have distorted trigonal bipyramidal geometry with HgN_4Cl and HgN_4Br chro-

separations are 4.135 \AA , 4.079 \AA and 4.117 \AA , respectively. Hg1 center in **1**, Hg3 and Hg5 centers in units 1 and 2 of **2** are deviated towards bridging halide by 0.621

Fig. 5. 2D sheet structure in **1** formed through N-H...Cl and C-H...Cl-hydrogen bonds along crystallographic *bc* plane.

Fig. 6. 2D sheet structure in **2** formed through N-H...Br and C-H...Br hydrogen bonds along crystallographic *bc* plane.

Table 1. Selected bond distances (Å) for **1** and **2**

Bond distances for 1		Bond distances for 2	
Hg1-N1	2.309(8)	Hg3-N1	2.310(15)
Hg1-N2	2.511(7)	Hg3-N3	2.355(18)
Hg1-N3	2.329(7)	Hg3-N10	2.338(14)
Hg1-N4	2.299(8)	Hg3-N13	2.488(16)
Hg1-Cl4	2.537(2)	Hg3-Br1	2.616(2)
Hg2-Cl1	2.437(2)	Hg4-Br1	2.784(2)
Hg2-Cl2	2.356(2)	Hg4-Br2	2.524(2)
Hg2-Cl3	2.456(2)	Hg4-Br3	2.573(2)
Hg2-Cl4	2.770(2)	Hg4-Br4	2.545(2)
		Hg5-N6	2.318(15)
		Hg5-N14	2.344(16)
		Hg5-N15	2.489(14)
		Hg5-N16	2.335(15)
		Hg5-Br5	2.637(2)
		Hg6-Br5	2.800(2)
		Hg6-Br6	2.558(2)
		Hg6-Br7	2.564(2)
		Hg6-Br8	2.538(2)

Å, 0.616 Å and 0.612 Å, respectively from the corresponding basal planes containing three N atoms (N1, N3, N4 for Hg1; N1, N3, N10 for Hg3; and N6, N14, N16 for Hg5) in **L**. The basal N atoms lie almost on the mean plane without any considerable deviations. The Hg-N and Hg-X (X = Cl, Br) bond distances are comparable with the literature values³⁵.

Tripodal amine (tren) has six hydrogen donor sites which form hydrogen bonds (Table 3) with the hydrogen acceptor chlorides/bromides. Each dinuclear unit in **1** is engaged through different N-H...Cl and C-H...Cl hy-

Table 2 Selected bond angles (°) for **1** and **2**

Bond angles for 1		Bond angles for 2	
N1-Hg1-N2	74.7(2)	N1-Hg3-N3	116.6(7)
N1-Hg1-N3	113.1(3)	N10-Hg3-N13	73.6(6)
		N10-Hg3-N13	76.4(5)

Table-2 (contd.)

N4-Hg1-N1	118.8(3)	N1-Hg3-N13	74.2(5)	N1-Hg3-Br1	102.8(4)
N4-Hg1-N3	107.1(3)	N10-Hg3-N3	114.3(7)	N3-Hg3-Br1	102.6(5)
N3-Hg1-N2	74.5(3)	N13-Hg3-Br1	172.9(3)	N10-Hg3-Br1	110.7(4)
N4-Hg1-N2	74.1(3)	Br2-Hg4-Br1	97.74(9)	Br3-Hg4-Br1	103.70(9)
N1-Hg1-Cl4	103.4(2)	Br4-Hg4-Br1	103.55(9)	Br2-Hg4-Br3	122.29(8)
N2-Hg1-Cl4	172.29(17)	Br2-Hg4-Br4	118.14(9)	Br4-Hg4-Br3	107.80(9)
N3-Hg1-Cl4	99.9(2)	Hg3-Br1-Hg4	98.06(8)	N6-Hg5-N15	74.5(5)
N4-Hg1-Cl4	113.0(2)	N6-Hg5-N14	117.6(6)	N14-Hg5-N15	75.3(5)
Cl2-Hg2-Cl11	126.96(9)	N6-Hg5-N16	113.8(5)	N6-Hg5-Br5	96.1(4)
Cl1-Hg2-Cl13	105.61(9)	N16-Hg5-N15	74.5(5)	N15-Hg5-Br5	169.6(3)
Cl1-Hg2-Cl4	94.75(8)	N14-Hg5-Br5	106.1(4)	Br6-Hg6-Br5	101.56(7)
Cl2-Hg2-Cl13	119.75(10)	N16-Hg5-Br5	114.1(4)	Br8-Hg6-Br5	102.71(8)
Cl2-Hg2-Cl4	103.29(9)	Br7-Hg6-Br5	104.15(8)	Br8-Hg6-Br6	119.11(9)
Cl3-Hg2-Cl4	98.94(8)	Br6-Hg6-Br7	110.42(9)	Hg5-Br5-Hg6	98.42(7)
Hg1-Cl4-Hg2	102.28(8)	Br8-Hg6-Br7	116.14(9)		

Table 3 Hydrogen bond distances (Å) and angles (°) for **1** and **2**

Compd.	D-H...A	D-H	H...A	D...A	D-H...A	Symmetry codes
1	N1-H1A...Cl2	0.90	2.76	3.564(9)	150.00	-1+x, y, z
	N1-H1B...Cl3	0.90	2.53	3.397(8)	161.00	2-x, 1/2+y, 3/2-z
	N3-H3A...Cl1	0.90	2.50	3.372(8)	163.00	2-x, 1/2+y, 3/2-z
	N3-H3B...Cl3	0.90	2.48	3.319(9)	156.00	-
	C3-H3C...Cl4	0.97	2.78	3.666(10)	152.00	2-x, -1/2+y, 3/2-z
2	N1-H1A...Br3	0.90	2.61	3.479(15)	161.00	1/2+x, 1/2-y, 1-z
	N1-H1B...Br3	0.90	2.82	3.533(15)	137.00	3/2-x, 1-y, 1/2+z
	N3-H3B...Br5	0.86	2.83	3.592(18)	148.00	1-x, -1/2+y, 1/2-z
	N6-H6B...Br1	0.90	2.82	3.589(16)	144.00	1-x, 1/2+y, 1/2-z
	N14-H14B...Br2	0.86	2.93	3.585(17)	135.00	-1+x, y, z
	C24-H24B...Br2	0.97	2.76	3.55(3)	139.00	3/2-x, 1-y, 1/2+z

Table 4. Crystal data and structure refinement for **1** and **2**

Crystal parameters	1	2
Empirical formula	C ₆ H ₁₈ N ₄ Cl ₄ Hg ₂	C ₆ H ₁₈ N ₄ Br ₄ Hg ₂
Formula weight	689.22	867.06
Crystal system	Monoclinic	Orthorhombic
Space group	P2(1)/c	P21
<i>a</i> (Å)	10.3822(19)	14.202(4)
<i>b</i> (Å)	11.501(2)	15.108(5)
<i>c</i> (Å)	13.034(3)	15.819(5)
β (°)	99.268(4)	90.00
<i>V</i> (Å ³)	1536.0(5)	3394.3(17)
λ (Å)	0.71073	0.71073
ρ _{calcd} (g cm ⁻³)	2.980	3.393
<i>Z</i>	4	8
Crystal size (mm ³)	0.24 × 0.22 × 0.20	0.20 × 0.18 × 0.16
Temperature (K)	293(2)	293(2)

Table-4 (contd.)

μ (mm ⁻¹)	20.643	27.471
$F(000)$	1240	3056
θ ranges (°)	1.99, 24.99	1.86, 25.00
$h/k/l$	-12/12, -13/13, -15/15	-16/16, -17/17, -17/18
Reflections collected	14149	24761
Independent reflections (R_{int})	2709	5965
T_{max} and T_{min}	0.016 and 0.010	0.006 and 0.012
Data/restraints/parameters	2709/0/146	5965/0/290
Goodness-of-fit on F^2	0.730	1.047
Final R indices [$I > 2\sigma(I)$]	$R = 0.0291$ and $wR = 0.0898$	$R = 0.0472$ and $wR = 0.0866$
Final R indices (all data)	$R = 0.0392$ and $wR = 0.1014$	$R = 0.0888$ and $wR = 0.0997$
Largest diff. peak and hole (eÅ ⁻³)	1.819 and -1.228	1.368 and -1.211
Weighting scheme : $R = \Sigma F_o - F_c /\Sigma F_o $, $wR = [\Sigma w(F_o^2 - F_c^2)^2/\Sigma w(F_o^2)^2]^{1/2}$, calcd. $w = 1/[\sigma^2(F_o^2) + (xP)^2 + yP]$; $x = 0.1000$ (for 1), 0.0000 (for 2) and $y = 0.8836$ (for 1), 0.0000 (for 2), where $P = (F_o^2 + 2F_c^2)/3$.		

drogen bonds forming a 2D sheet structure (Fig. 5) along crystallographic bc plane with different cyclic motifs like $R^2_2(8)$, $R^2_2(12)$ and $R^4_4(16)$ in Etter's graph notation³⁶. Two dinuclear units in compound **2** are associated through N-H...Br and C-H...Br hydrogen bonds to form a 2D sheet structure (Fig. 6) along crystallographic bc plane.

Conclusion

Two neutral halide bridged dinuclear coordination molecules have been isolated through single-pot reactions of the molecular building components in preassigned molar ratios. X-Ray crystallographic study of the compounds **1** and **2** shows two different mercury(II) centers with T_d and tbp geometry. This work demonstrates that the soft mercury(II) ion is able to form compounds with varied coordination numbers, viz. four and five through judicious choice of the ligands and thereby afford different crystalline architectures in long-range forms. Such variation of superstructures shows how composition may tailor topology with different networks through malleable strong coordination covalent bonds and lateral multiple weak non-covalent forces. The preparation of such compounds illustrates a potentially versatile approach to the construction of uncharged metal-organic frameworks.

Experimental

Materials and methods :

High purity tris(2-aminoethyl)amine (Fluka, Germany), mercury(II) chloride (E. Merck, India) and mercury(II) bromide (E. Merck, India) were purchased from respective concerns and used as received. All other chemicals

and solvents used were AR grade. The synthetic reactions and work-up were done in open air.

Elemental analyses (carbon, hydrogen and nitrogen) were performed on a Perkin-Elmer 2400 CHNS/O elemental analyzer. IR spectra (KBr discs, 4000–400 cm⁻¹) were recorded using a Perkin-Elmer FTIR model RX1 spectrometer. Molar conductances were measured using a Systronics conductivity meter where the cell constant was calibrated with 0.01(M) KCl solution, and MeCN was used as solvent. Thermal behaviors were examined with a Perkin-Elmer Diamond TG/DT analyzer heated from 30–700 °C under nitrogen. Ground state absorptions measurements (in DMF) were made with a Shimadzu model UV-2450 UV-Vis spectrophotometer.

Preparation of the complexes :

$[(L)Hg(\mu-Cl)HgCl_3]$ (**1**) and $[(L)Hg(\mu-Br)HgBr_3]$ (**2**) :

A colorless methanolic solution (20 ml) of L (0.073 g, 0.5 mmol) was added dropwise to a solution of HgCl₂ (0.271 g, 1 mmol) in the same solvent (20 ml). The resulting colorless solution was filtered and the supernatant liquid was kept undisturbed in open air for slow evaporation. After a few days rectangular crystalline product of **1** was isolated by filtration, washed with dehydrated alcohol and dried *in vacuo* over silica gel. Yield : 0.448 g (65%). For preparation and isolation of **2** in pure crystalline state, similar reaction condition and reaction stoichiometry as used in **1** were followed except that HgBr₂ (0.360 g, 1 mmol) instead of HgCl₂ was used. Yield : 0.624 g (72%). Found : C, 10.6; H, 2.4; N, 8.2%. Calcd. C₆H₁₈N₄Cl₄Hg₂ (**1**) : C, 10.5; H, 2.6; N, 8.1; IR (KBr,

cm^{-1}) : $\nu(\text{C-H})$ 2979, 2935; $\nu(\text{N-H})$ 3148, 3255, 3276, 3308, 3339; UV-Vis (DMF, $\lambda_{\text{max}}/\text{nm}$) : 263; Λ_{M} (MeCN, $\Omega^{-1} \text{cm}^2 \text{mol}^{-1}$) : 6. Found : C, 8.5; H, 2.3; N, 6.3%. Calcd. $\text{C}_6\text{H}_{18}\text{N}_4\text{Br}_4\text{Hg}_2$ (**2**) : C, 8.3; H, 2.1; N, 6.5; IR (KBr, cm^{-1}) : $\nu(\text{C-H})$ 2972, 2927; $\nu(\text{N-H})$ 3152, 3248, 3274, 3304; UV-Vis (DMF, $\lambda_{\text{max}}/\text{nm}$) : 258; Λ_{M} (MeCN, $\Omega^{-1} \text{cm}^2 \text{mol}^{-1}$) : 7.

X-Ray crystallographic analyses :

Single crystals of **1** and **2** suitable for X-ray analyses were selected from those obtained by slow evaporation of methanolic solutions at room temperature. Diffraction data were collected on a Bruker SMART APEX-II CCD area-detector diffractometer (293 K) using graphite monochromated Mo-K α radiation ($\lambda = 0.71073 \text{ \AA}$). For unit cell determination, the single crystal was exposed with X-ray for 10 s in three frames. The detector frames were integrated by use of the program SAINT³⁷ and absorption corrections were performed with SADABS³⁸. The structures were solved by direct methods, using the SHELXTL³⁹ program. All atomic displacement parameters for non-hydrogen atoms have been refined with anisotropic term. For all structures, the hydrogen atoms were fixed geometrically and refined using a riding model. All calculations were carried out using SHELXTL, PLATON⁴⁰ and ORTEP-3⁴¹ programs. Further details are given in Table 4.

Supplementary data

Crystallographic data for the structural analysis have been deposited with the Cambridge Crystallographic Data Center, Nos. 914665 (**1**) and 914666 (**2**). Copies of this information can be had free of charge from The Director, CCDC, 12 Union Road, Cambridge, CB2 1EZ, UK (Fax : +44-1223-336033; E-mail : deposit@ccdc.cam.ac.uk or <http://www.ccdc.cam.ac.uk>).

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